

(Table 2). Longer than 1 wk decomposition had no significant effect. Although high ESP significantly reduced biomass turnover and N contribution of sesbania, it had no effect on yield. ESP levels were substantially reduced after harvest. □

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Physiology and plant nutrition

Influence of new terpenoid analogue of abscisic acid on chilling resistance of rice seedlings

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We studied the effect of the new terpenoid analogue of abscisic acid of the acetylene-acetate type coded LAB 173711 (see figure) on resistance to chilling in 14-d-old rice seedlings.

Seedlings were sprayed with LAB 173711, at 10^{-3} mol/liter, maintained in a glasshouse at 29/ 21 °C day/night temperature, 12 h photoperiod, and 80% relative humidity for 24 h, then transferred to a chamber at 5 °C temperature for 3 and 5 d. Recovery in the glasshouse was monitored for several days.

Survival in unprotected plants chilled for 3 d was 60% 2 d after treatment (DAT); no plants survived 5 DAT (Table 1). Plants sprayed with LAB

173711 had 100% survival. The number of plants surviving 5 °C for 5 d was similar.

The analogue also protected the root system (Table 2). The number of

adventitious roots, root length, and root weight were higher in treated plants. The stability of the root system may contribute to the increased survival rate in protected plants. The increase in chilling tolerance may also be due to the direct action of analogue 173711 on stomatal closure; that prevented water loss through transpiration. □

Table 1. Survival of rice plants treated with LAB 173711, chilled at 5 °C for 3 and 5 d, and returned to 29 °C for recovery. Data are means ± SE of 3 parallel experiments with 10 plants each.

Treatment	Survival (%) with given time at 29 °C				
	1 d	2 d	4 d	6 d	8 d
<i>Chilled for 3 d</i>					
Control	100.0 ± 0	60.0 ± 5.8	23.33 ± 6.6	0	0
With 173711	100.0 ± 0	100.0 ± 0	100.0 ± 0	100.0 ± 0	100.0 ± 0
<i>Chilled for 5 d</i>					
Control	100.0 ± 0	44.0 ± 3.2	0	0	0
With 173711	100.0 ± 0	74.0 ± 6.6	68.0 ± 11.1	30.0 ± 4.1	30.0 ± 4.1

Table 2. Root growth of rice plants treated with LAB 173711, chilled at 5 °C for 2 d, and returned to 29 °C for 7 d recovery.^a

Treatment	Nodal roots ^a (no./plant)	Length ^b (cm)	Fresh weight ^b (mg)	Dry weight ^b (mg)
Control	17.0 ± 1.8	9.9 ± 1.2	205.8 ± 28.3	27.7 ± 7.0
173711	26.2 ± 1.7	14.7 ± 2.2	770.8 ± 28.0	69.2 ± 7.0

^a Data are means ± SE of 5 measurements. ^b Data are means ±SE of 8 measurements.

Chemical structures of abscisic acid (ABA) and of its terpenoid analogue LAB 173711.

Crop management

Effect of planting overage seedlings on rice duration, yield, and yield attributes

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Varietal differences in growth duration are due primarily to differences in length of the vegetative phase. We studied 15 prerelease cultures and varieties in the 1983 wet season. The field experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with three replications. Due to an unprecedented severe drought, 54-d-old seedlings were transplanted at 2-3 seedlings/hill spaced 15 × 15 cm.

The maturity of short-duration varieties (95-120 d) was prolonged to